

**The Ethics of Minimum Equipment List Usage in Aviation:
Balancing Operational Efficiency and Safety**

Minnesota State University, Mankato

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Nathan Kachelmyer

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It's early evening at a busy east coast airport with good weather. While an airline crew is doing the routine walk around between flights the First Officer notices a discrepancy during the inspection. The aircraft's green wingtip position light is not illuminating. This is a required light used by other aircraft to determine relative position, especially at night.

This particular airport does not have company maintenance. However, it is still daylight, and the flight is scheduled to return to base where the issue can be repaired. If the First Officer informs the Captain (or PIC, Pilot-in-Command), the discrepancy must be entered into the aircraft logbook and contract maintenance will need to be called. That will delay the flight, possibly significantly.

There are passengers on board with tight connections. A delay here won't just affect this flight, it will likely ripple through multiple legs across the system. Additionally, both pilots are commuters, planning to catch the last flight home after their arrival. A delay would likely mean an unplanned overnight, a hotel at their own expense, and lost time at home.

From a practical standpoint, the inoperative position light appears to have little impact on safety for an operating the flight.

So, the question becomes: What should the First Officer do?

Now consider a second scenario.

The same discrepancy is found, but this time the aircraft is at a home base airport. Maintenance is available and can respond within minutes. The flight is the last leg of the day to

an overnight, and none of the passengers have connections. The operational and personal pressures are significantly reduced.

The safety question, however, is the same: What should the First Officer do?

Scenarios like this play out every day in aviation. Flight crews and maintenance personnel are constantly making decisions that balance safety, operational efficiency, cost, and personal pressures. There is regulatory guidance, such as the FAA's MEL (minimum equipment list) framework, that defines what is legally permissible. However, as is often the case in aviation, legal does not always mean ethical.

This paper argues that while MEL usage provides a structured and legally compliant method to manage inoperative equipment, its ethical application depends on how those decisions are made.

When operational pressures begin to influence decisions that should be grounded in conservative risk management, the intent of the MEL can shift from a safety tool to a means of maintaining operational continuity. Using ethical frameworks such as utilitarianism and virtue ethics, this paper examines where that line exists, and how aviation professionals, particularly the PIC, must navigate that boundary to ensure safety remains the primary standard.

Before we discuss the ethical operation of an MEL, we should have a firm understanding of what an MEL is, in both its functional and practical application.

Regulatory authority: Under FAR (Federal Aviation Regulations) 91.213 and the additional requirements governing 14 CFR (Code of Federal Regulations) Part 121, operators are provided with a structured legal framework that allows certain aircraft systems to be inoperative, provided they are addressed through an approved MEL. These regulations establish the baseline

legal authority to dispatch an aircraft with deferred items, but they also define the conditions, limitations, and required procedures that must be followed. This framework is further supported by guidance in FAA Advisory Circular 120-125 and international standards such as ICAO Annex 6 Part I, both of which reinforce that the MEL is intended as a controlled risk management tool, not a blanket approval to operate the aircraft in a downgraded state. These sources make it clear that MEL use is built on predefined limitations, procedures, and assumptions about risk. From an operator's standpoint, this shifts the decision-making from "is it allowed?" to "is it appropriate in this context?" It places responsibility on the PIC, maintenance, and dispatch to treat regulatory compliance not as the ceiling of safety, but as the floor upon which sound judgment and risk management are applied.

As part of the aircraft certification and airworthiness requirements an aircraft cannot be dispatched to operate in service with any inoperative equipment, or system, unless this is allowed the MEL and under the applicable conditions. Commonly, the MEL mirrors the Master MEL (MMEL), which is developed by the manufacturer and approved by the regulator. However, the increasing complexity of aircraft systems and the diversity of operational requirements, environmental conditions, fleet configurations, etc., necessitates a tailored approach to developing the MEL.

Under ideal conditions, everything would work perfectly, all the time. However, not everything is always ideal. For example, "a Boeing 737 MAX has roughly *500,000 parts*—and if you count every rivet and fastener individually, that number jumps to around *2 million parts*." (Memon, 2023). At some point, something is eventually going to break or unexpectedly or quit working. So, the purpose of the MEL is to list every item and categorize, classify, and determine the effectiveness of it not functioning in relation to operating the aircraft. Every item is listed

under its respective category; ex. 22-Auto Flight, 23-Communications, 24-Electrical Power, 25 – Equipment and Furnishings, etc.) Under each section is a numerical subsection, and that is broken down into two more sub-sections. For the following examples we will use an A320 (Airbus 320) example, aircraft landing lights; 33-40-02-01 – Landing Light System. Each item is listed with five corresponding parts steps.

1. If the flight crew can defer the item or maintenance personnel need to perform the deferral.
2. The maximum repair time interval required for that specific item. MEL repair intervals define the maximum allowable time an inoperative item can remain deferred before it must be repaired, categorized as A, B, C, or D.

Category A is specified individually in the MEL (case-by-case), B is within 3 days, C within 10 days, and D within 120 days (all excluding the day of discovery).
3. Number of items or systems installed on the aircraft; ex. landing lights (2) installed.
4. Number of items or systems installed required for the aircraft to be dispatched; ex. landing lights (1) required.
5. The final step is the procedure. The procedure step is specified instructions for flight to operations with the inoperative equipment; ex landing light – no special procedure required.

After these steps are followed, the discrepancy is documented in the aircraft's logbook and with the operator, and the aircraft is allowed to be operated with the inoperable component or system.

The purpose of an MEL is to provide a structured and approved way to operate an aircraft with certain inoperative systems while still maintaining an acceptable level of safety. It allows

operators to keep the aircraft in service without compromising the overall integrity of the flight, as long as the conditions and limitations are followed. However, this is where the ethical line starts to blur. The MEL is not intended to be a loophole to defer maintenance or to keep pushing the airplane for the sake of schedule, cost, or convenience. The risk is normalization; that over time, what was meant to be an exception can start to feel normal. The mindset can shift from *Is this the right call?* to *It's legal, so let's go*. From a crewmember standpoint, that's where judgment and experience comes into play. Just because the MEL allows operation doesn't automatically mean it's the right or safest decision in or best course of action.

The ethical dilemma in MEL usage arises when a deferral is legally permissible but still feels operationally or morally questionable within the broader safety context. In other words, legal does not always mean ethical. Pilots and maintenance personnel must balance regulatory compliance with real-time risk. Often under operational pressures (on-time performance, cost, dispatch reliability), where the ethical challenge lies in deciding whether legal aligns responsibly with safe and in that given moment.

An ethical issue with the operational use of MEL where the deferral of a malfunctioning part is allowed but may still be questionable on an operational, and/or moral level to the overall context of safety. In other words, being legal does not always equate to being ethical. The pilot and maintenance crew members are burdened with the need to comply with the regulations and then weigh that against the risk at that very moment. The pilot and maintenance crews are usually working under considerable pressures such as on-time performance, costs, and reliability of getting and keeping the aircraft in operation. The ultimate question becomes whether being legal, means that it is safe and responsible given all the elements of that particular point in time

The use of the MEL in aviation is ethically justified when applied within regulatory compliance and sound judgment; however, its misuse, when driven by operational pressure, normalization of deviance, or economic incentives, can hurt safety margins and can put pilots and maintenance personnel in ethically complex decision-making situations that demand adherence to professional integrity and safety-first principles.

Ethical Frameworks Applied to MEL Usage - Key Ethical Theories

Utilitarianism

From a utilitarian perspective, MEL usage may be justified if it results in the greatest good for the greatest number. Dispatching a flight avoids widespread delays, passenger disruptions, and financial losses. However, this approach can become ethically dangerous when it justifies incremental increases in risk. Having a flight depart on time and running an on-time operation reduces the overall effects of having an extended delay, and other disruptions to passengers, the downstream effects of issues and the airline's financial exposure. Even having one delayed or cancelled flight can have far-reaching impacts and ripple out in an airline's entire network and affect thousands of passengers and numerous crew members as well. Using an MEL to keep the operation going can be viewed as providing the greatest good.

The ethical dilemma, however, arises as MEL usage becomes normalized, it begins the process of normalizing incremental increases in risk (Reason, 1997). The danger does not lie within any one single MEL deferral but rather within the creating of a pattern of "just a little more" or, "we know we can operate fine without it, just write it up when we get there," risk being accepted each time. While having a legally compliant MEL usage decision may evolve into a pattern to where operational convenience, and airline reliability can exceed the acceptable

safety margins over time. This is where utilitarianism and the foundational principles of safety in aviation are in conflict; since the "greatest good" is often measured by efficiency and the outcome, rather than the absence of an accident. This is an important point from a PIC perspective. The consequence of having a negative outcome if the operation doesn't proceed as intended is extraordinarily large. One event can negate the potential good created by thousands of "acceptable" flights that were carried out in a similar manner. This type of ethical reasoning often minimizes the low-probability, high-consequence events; however, aviation is designed as an ultra-safe system where those risks can never be completely discounted, and worst case must always be considered (Hansson, 2003; ICAO, 2013).

Operational pressures also contribute to this situation. Ethically framing the decision around a broader system, impact (on-time performance, passenger satisfaction, and costs) can lead to more credibility to the utilitarian argument (often unwittingly). The sum of all such facts may result in a gradual shift of the process to make it no longer be "Is this the safest decision?" to "Is this acceptable within the operating system?" These are two very distinct questions. Although utilitarianism serves a purpose in addressing operational impacts of MEL usage, it cannot serve as the primary ethical framework for such MEL usage. Aviation safety is not based on creating the highest level of efficiency; it is based on conservative and deliberate risk management. The line gets crossed when the goal changes, from operating safely within limits to simply keeping the airline operation moving, even if those limits are being pushed.

Deontological Ethics

Deontological, or duty-based, ethics emphasizes obligation over outcome. Within a deontological framework, the PIC has a non-negotiable duty to ensure the safety of the flight. Even when dispatch under an MEL is legally permissible, it may still be ethically unacceptable if

it compromises any safety margins. This duty and obligation is backed up by 14 CFR § 91.3, which establishes that the PIC is directly responsible for, and the final authority on, the operation of the aircraft.

Deontological ethics is most closely associated with the work of Immanuel Kant (1724–1804), who based morality on duty and the concept of the categorical imperative. This principle holds that an action is only morally acceptable if it can be applied universally as a rule governing all rational behavior (Kant, 1785/1993). Within this framework, there is little grey area—actions are either right or wrong. While this clarity provides a strong ethical standard, it can also make deontological ethics difficult to apply in practice, particularly in complex, real-world situations where decisions involve uncertainty and competing pressures (Hoppe, 2020).

Applied to aviation, deontological ethics asks a simple question: if every pilot made the same decision under the same MEL conditions, would the system remain safe? If the answer is uncertain, the decision is ethically questionable. From this perspective, the PIC's responsibility is not to weigh efficiency or system benefit, but to uphold an absolute duty to safety.

This rigidity of deontological ethics can make it difficult to apply in real-world operations. Often decisions are made under conditions of uncertainty, time pressure, and competing demands. However, that same rigidity serves an important protective function. In an environment where incremental risk-taking can become normalized, a duty-based framework establishes a clear boundary that resists the gradual erosion of safety margins (Reason, 1997).

In the context of MEL usage, this means that even if a decision is operationally efficient or systemically beneficial, it is not ethically justified if it conflicts with the PIC's fundamental obligation to safety. The presence of operational pressures, schedule, cost, or passenger impact,

does not change that obligation. Deontological ethics ultimately reinforces a simple but essential principle: the duty to maintain safety is not negotiable.

Virtue Ethics

What is virtue ethics? Virtue ethics asks a different question: *What would a good captain do?* This framework emphasizes professional integrity, judgment, and character. As noted by Aristotle, virtue is developed through habit and practice, where excellence becomes a consistent way of acting rather than a one-time decision. A pilot guided by virtue does not look for the minimum acceptable standard but instead strives for the highest standard of safety.

Virtue ethics examines the character of the individual deciding, instead of examining either just the outcome of the decision or the process used to reach the outcome (rules). Virtue ethics provides a new perspective to the question of "What would a good captain do?" Ethical decision-making in aviation is not only about compliance, but also about the professional character and judgment applied in an operational context (Hoppe, 2020). With this framework in mind, it is easy for a Captain to have integrity, good judgment and moral character. For MEL purposes, the focus changes from the minimum that is required to operate legally or operationally, to completing the tasks of flying the aircraft while exhibiting the highest standard of airmanship.

Virtuous pilots do not look for the minimum standard for safety; they look for the highest standard. They do not ask "Can we go?" but instead ask "Should we go?" That way of thinking comes from discipline, experience, and a personal standard of excellence, not because operational oversight demands it, but because they do.

From the perspective of a PIC, virtue ethics reinforces the belief that making safety decisions is not solely a procedural matter; it is also a personal matter. The way the Captain sets the tone for crew and operation of the flight, and by extension, MEL usage. When the Captain makes decisions based solely on professionalism and integrity, the MEL will continue to be what it was intended to be: a controlled, conservative instrument, not a method by which to simply keep the the operation moving.

In practice, the application of virtue ethics typically occurs during uncertain situations. The deferral may be legally compliant, however, the circumstances, such as weather, workload, fatigue or redundancy of the system may make the Captain hesitate. Virtue ethics will provide the Captain with an opportunity to step back and consider, what may legally compliant, does not have to be right for that day. This type of judgment is difficult to document, but rather learned through experience and based on the Captain's character. Virtue ethics establishes the source of responsibility at the point it belongs; with the professional located in the left seat. There is an expectation of not only legal compliance, but also of excellence in how they accomplish their responsibilities.

Risk Ethics

Risk ethics introduces the concept of acceptable versus unacceptable risk. MEL usage inherently involves accepting some level of risk, but ethical decision-making requires evaluating whether that risk remains within acceptable boundaries, especially when compounded by other factors such as weather or operational complexity. What level of risk is reasonable? To whom, and for what? These are just some basic questions asked in the field of risk ethics. Hansson paper on risk ethics argues that ethical decision making involves identifying a risk and determining if it is (1) justified, (2) necessary, and (3) equitably apportioned among those affected by it, the field

of aviation highlights the significant relationship between risk and ethics because almost every operational decision requires some acceptance of risk.

In aviation operations, the use of an MEL is a way to operate a flight that is dispatched with an "acceptable" risk(s) when one of a pre-defined number of aircraft systems (i.e., an MEL-listed item) has been identified as inoperative (subject to the specific operational conditions). In this case the MEL acts as a framework that assumes that there are other systems (which, individually, may have varying degrees of reliability, and redundancy) and procedures and or limitations that will allow for an overall acceptable level of risk.

Therefore, identification of the expected acceptable level of risk as defined by an MEL is not a static risk assessment but is instead dynamic. From a risk ethics perspective, a decision to utilize an MEL does not mean that an aircraft operational risk will remain within acceptable limits, but that the assessment of risk must involve a complete view of the whole operational risk present, and the overall operational risk associated with that flight being operated.

For example, although there may be a specific deferred item (inoperative system) that is not considered to increase the risk of flight when considered alone, when combined with other contributing factors, the overall total risk may exceed an acceptable threshold. In this regard, risk assessment in aviation requires a larger view than the assessment of the individual item(s).

Additionally, the definition of acceptable risk is subjective based on those who are exposed to the associated risks (Hansson, 2003). For purposes of aviation, those individuals include not only the flight crew, but also all passengers and other individuals on the ground. All of these individuals would be considered to be stakeholders; however, none of these individuals are typically involved in the decision-making process with respect to the risks associated with

that particular flight. Consequently, the PIC has an ethical obligation to exercise sound judgment in making risk assessments and determinations.

The risk ethics principles align directly with FAR 91.3, where the PIC is both legally responsible for the safety of the flight and ethically obligated to ensure that acceptable risk limits are not exceeded. That responsibility exists regardless of outcome. Just because nothing happened doesn't make it the right decision, it only means you got away with it that time.

From a practical standpoint, risk ethics highlights the danger of incremental risk acceptance. The presence of an MEL item does not automatically make the operation acceptable. The total operational risk must be evaluated as a total picture. Threats like the weather, aircraft system status, and passengers, overall operational complexity, all considered together as a single risk profile, not as individual pieces.

This is really where pilot experience becomes critically important, and it should not be confused with normalization. Experience provides judgment, and the ability to recognize when multiple small risks are beginning to stack in a way that erodes safety margins. Normalization, on the other hand, is the gradual acceptance of those same risks simply because they have been encountered before and there weren't any consequences.

In summary, risk ethics highlights two key principles: (1) not all acceptable risks carry the same weight, and (2) not all legal risks are ethical.

Human Factors and Decision-Making Pressures

"We cannot change the human condition, but we can change the conditions under which humans work." — (Reason, 2000).

The ethical dilemma regarding Minimum Equipment List (MEL) usage arises when a deferral is legally permissible but operationally questionable. Under FAR 91.3, the Pilot in Command (PIC) is ultimately responsible for the safety of the flight, which extends beyond regulatory compliance. Legal does not always mean ethical, particularly in aviation decision-making where operational pressures are present (Hansson, 2003; Munro & Kanki, 2003).

MEL as a Risk Management Tool, Not a Loophole

The MEL is designed as a structured risk management tool that allows aircraft to operate safely with certain inoperative systems. It is not intended to be used as a way for aircraft operators to permanently or chronically, defer items or systems installed on the aircraft. From a risk ethics perspective, an acceptable risk is not solely determined by regulatory thresholds but by whether the risk is justified, equitable, and necessary within the operational context. Risk acceptance must consider both the probability of harm and the moral justification for exposing others to that risk (Hansson, 2003). Applied to MEL usage, this means that even if a deferral falls into or within regulatory allowances, it must still be evaluated against the total operational risk environment, including cumulative system degradations. According to the FAA, MELs are intended to “permit safe operation of aircraft with inoperative equipment under specific conditions” (Federal Aviation Administration, 2014). If the PIC determines for any reason that a flight cannot be conducted or operated in a safe manner or, safety may somehow be jeopardized, they have the ethical obligation to refuse acceptance and the operation of the aircraft.

Operational Pressures and Ethical Drift

Operational pressures such as on-time performance and cost control can influence decision-making in ways that gradually normalize higher levels of risk. Research on aeronautical

decision-making has shown that time pressure can significantly affect how pilots process information and recognize cues, even at high levels of expertise (Stokes et al., 1991). Research has also shown that maintenance-related decision-making can be influenced by systemic pressures rather than individual intent (Munro & Kanki, 2003). In the airline environment, these pressures are rarely explicit, but they are consistently present, delays impact network flow, passenger connections, crew legality, and overall operational efficiency. Over time, this environment can subtly shift the decision-making mindset from one focused on conservative risk management to one focused on maintaining operational continuity.

From a human factors perspective, this shift represents a form of *ethical drift*, where the standard for what is considered acceptable gradually changes without conscious recognition. Diane Vaughan identified this pattern in complex, high-reliability systems, noting that repeated exposure to risk without negative outcomes can recalibrate judgment. Similarly, research in aviation maintenance and operations has shown that organizational and economic pressures can shape behavior in ways that make marginal decisions feel routine rather than exceptional (Hobbs, 2008; Munro & Kanki, 2003). The danger is not that individuals intentionally accept unsafe conditions, but that the system itself slowly redefines what is perceived as safe.

From a PIC perspective, this creates a critical responsibility to recognize when external pressures are influencing internal decision-making. The presence of an MEL deferral may be legally acceptable, but when combined with operational pressures, it requires a deliberate pause to ensure that the decision is still grounded in sound risk assessment rather than convenience. Left unchecked, these pressures can erode safety margins incrementally, reinforcing the importance of disciplined judgment and a consistent safety-first mindset in all operational decisions.

Normalization of Deviance

Repeated exposure to MEL dispatches can lead to normalization of deviance, where abnormal conditions become accepted as routine. What begins as a justified exception gradually becomes standard practice.

Repeated exposure to aircraft being dispatched with MELs can lead to what is commonly referred to as *normalization of deviance*, a concept introduced by Diane Vaughan in her analysis of the Space Shuttle Challenger disaster. Normalization of deviance occurs when deviations from standard practice, initially recognized as abnormal, gradually become accepted as routine through repeated exposure without immediate negative consequences.

In aviation operations, this concept is particularly relevant to MEL usage. What begins as a justified and risk-assessed deferral that is fully compliant with regulatory guidance, can, over time, become operationally routine. As Federal Aviation Administration guidance makes clear, the MEL is intended as a controlled risk management tool, not a mechanism for consistent operation in a degraded state. However, when flight crews, maintenance personnel, and dispatchers are repeatedly exposed to aircraft operating under MEL provisions without incident, there is a natural tendency to recalibrate what is perceived as “normal.”

This gradual shift in perception can slowly erode critical risk awareness. As demonstrated, the absence of adverse outcomes reinforces the belief that the risk is acceptable, even when the underlying hazard remains unchanged (Vaughan, 1996). In other words, safe outcomes do not necessarily validate the decision they may simply indicate that safety margins were not exceeded on that occasion.

From a human factors perspective, this aligns with findings in aviation maintenance research, where systemic pressures and repeated exposure to minor deviations can influence decision-making over time (Munro & Kanki, 2003). The danger is not in just having an aircraft with a single MEL deferral, but it's the cumulative effect of having repeated deferrals that slowly change the operational baseline.

From a risk ethics standpoint, this creates critical concern. Acceptable risk must be evaluated not only by regulatory allowance, but by whether the risk remains justified under changing conditions (Hansson, 2003). Normalization of deviance undermines this evaluation by masking incremental increases in operational risk.

Normalizing deviance ultimately causes a disciplined method of assessing risks to be ineffective. The PIC must resist the temptation to consider repeated exposures as equating to safe, and continuously re-evaluate whether a particular MEL deferral is still justified as a result of the overall risk environment.

Completion Bias

Completion bias, which is often referred to in aviation as “get-there-itis”, and it is a well-documented trap in human factors where the desire to complete a mission begins to outweigh objective risk assessment. Research has shown that emotional and cognitive factors can significantly influence pilot decision-making under pressure (Causse et al., 2013). For flight crews, this pressure is not often very visible. It can often come from subtle operational influences such as maintaining the schedule, avoiding passenger disruptions, or simply the natural inclination to finish what was started and go home. When a mechanical issue appears minor, particularly one that is MEL-deferred and therefore legally permissible, it becomes easier to

rationalize and just continue the flight rather than reassessing the broader operational risk. In this way, the presence of an MEL can unintentionally reinforce the completion bias by providing a regulatory justification that aligns with the crew's desire to proceed.

Human factors frameworks such as the Human Factors Analysis and Classification System (HFACS) identify this behavior as a form of decision error shaped by both internal motivations and external pressures (Shappell & Wiegmann, 2000). Importantly, this is not a failure of professionalism, it is a predictable cognitive tendency under operational conditions. As highlighted in Federal Aviation Administration guidance on aeronautical decision-making, pilots must continuously evaluate whether changing conditions alter the risk profile of the flight, regardless of initial legality or dispatch status (FAA-H-8083-2A). From a PIC authority standpoint, the critical distinction is recognizing that the successful completion of a flight does not validate the decision-making process. It only indicates that the margin was not exceeded on that particular occasion. The ethical responsibility remains to challenge continuation bias in real time, especially when multiple small risks begin to align into a larger operational threat

Weather and Environmental Factors

An MEL item that is acceptable in one context may be unacceptable in another. Weather and environmental conditions are great examples of how those variables can change operational risk. For example, dispatching with reduced anti-ice capability in marginal icing conditions introduces increases the risk that may not be fully captured by MEL guidance alone. While the MEL may legally permit the operation, it cannot account for real-time variability such as un-forecast icing intensity, temperature deviations, or the cumulative effects of moisture exposure over the course of the flight.

From an operational standpoint, environmental factors compound risk rather than simply add to it. A single deferred system may be manageable in isolation, but when combined with adverse weather, reduced performance margins, or limited diversion options, the overall risk profile changes significantly. This is consistent with aeronautical decision-making principles emphasized by the Federal Aviation Administration, which stress continuous risk assessment as conditions evolve rather than reliance on initial dispatch legality alone. From a PIC authority perspective, this reinforces a critical point: MEL guidance defines what is permissible, but it does not replace the responsibility to evaluate whether the conditions of the day support a safe outcome.

Maintenance Pressure

Maintenance personnel often operate within a regulatory framework that emphasizes compliance as the primary standard: if the aircraft meets the MEL, it is considered airworthy for dispatch. However, research in aviation maintenance ethics highlights that compliance alone does not always address the broader ethical responsibility for safety (Patankar, 2005). On its surface, that logic is both correct and necessary. However, a strict “if it’s legal, it’s good” mindset can unintentionally narrow the decision-making lens and overlook the broader operational context in which that aircraft will actually be flown. Regulatory compliance establishes the minimum acceptable standard—it does not necessarily define the safest or most prudent course of action in a dynamic operational environment.

From an operational standpoint, maintenance decisions do not occur in isolation. They are influenced by external pressures such as schedule reliability, cost control, aircraft availability, and organizational expectations. As Federal Aviation Administration guidance in Advisory Circular 120-125 emphasizes, the MEL is intended as a controlled risk management tool—not a

mechanism to normalize degraded system operations indefinitely (FAA, 2014a). When compliance becomes the endpoint rather than the starting point for risk evaluation, the system begins to accept incremental risk without fully appreciating its cumulative effect.

Frameworks such as Human Factors Analysis and Classification System (HFACS), SHELL Model, and PEAR Model reinforce that these decisions are rarely the result of a single individual's judgment. Instead, they are shaped by latent organizational conditions, supervisory influences, and environmental factors (Shappell & Wiegmann, 2000; Federal Aviation Administration, n.d.). HFACS, for example, identifies how organizational climate and resource management can create conditions where frontline personnel feel compelled to prioritize dispatch reliability over conservative decision-making. Similarly, the SHELL model highlights mismatches between the individual (Liveware) and their environment, whether procedural, technical, or organizational, that can degrade decision quality under pressure (Hawkins, F. H., 1987; International Civil Aviation Organization, 1998). The PEAR model, widely used in maintenance human factors, explicitly recognizes "Resources" and "Environment" as key drivers, underscoring how time pressure, staffing, and operational demand directly influence maintenance actions (Federal Aviation Administration, 2014; Alan Hobbs, 2008).

Within this context, MEL misuse is rarely intentionally malicious. It is more accurately understood as a form of organizational drift, where repeated exposure to acceptable risk conditions gradually shifts the boundary of what is considered "normal" (Dekker, 2006). Over time, deferrals that were once approached with caution can become routine, not because they are inherently unsafe, but because the system has adapted to their presence. Analysis of ASRS maintenance reports that MEL-related issues often reflected breakdowns in communication, coordination, and situational awareness rather than intentional non-compliance (Munro and

Kanki, 2003). This reinforces the idea that the ethical challenge is not simply about following the rules, but about recognizing when adherence to the minimum standard is no longer sufficient given the total operational picture.

From a PIC authority perspective, this creates a critical point where maintenance and flight operations intersect. The aircraft may be legally dispatched, but the ethical responsibility to evaluate the cumulative risk still remains. A deferral that is acceptable by itself, may carry different implications when combined with weather, route structure, crew experience, or other additional deferred items. This is where the distinction between legal compliance and ethical judgment becomes operationally significant. The system may permit the dispatch, but that does not remove the obligation to question whether it should occur.

Ethical Dilemmas in MEL Usage

Situations may arise where maintenance signs off an aircraft as legal, but the PIC remains uncomfortable. This creates a direct ethical conflict between compliance and judgment. The following is a case study of such an incident.

Case Study: Compounding MEL Risk in Flight Operations

The following is a summary of the NASA ACN: 1896253

An airline flight was dispatched with one engine-driven generator (IDG) deferred in accordance with the MEL, which required the auxiliary power unit (APU) to remain operational throughout the flight to provide redundancy. The aircraft had already completed multiple legs earlier in the day with the same deferred item and no additional issues reported. Shortly after reaching cruise altitude, the APU automatically shut down, leaving the aircraft with a single remaining source of AC electrical power. Recognizing the loss of redundancy, the crew requested

priority handling and diverted to a nearby airport, where the aircraft landed without further incident. While the outcome was uneventful, the situation resulted in a significantly degraded electrical system that exceeded the intended safety assumptions underlying the MEL dispatch.

This case illustrates how MEL decisions that are individually compliant can create elevated risk when considered collectively. The initial deferral of the IDG was consistent with MEL guidance, and subsequent uneventful flights reinforced the perception that the aircraft was operating normally. However, the MEL assumption, that the APU would remain available as a backup power source, became a single point of weakness once the aircraft continued operating in that degraded state over multiple legs.

From a risk-ethics perspective, this reflects the distinction between acceptable and justified risk. While each individual dispatch met regulatory requirements, the cumulative exposure to risk increased with each additional flight, ultimately resulting in a loss of system redundancy that exceeded the intended safety margin (Hansson, 2003). This pattern is consistent with the concept of normalization of deviance, where repeated successful outcomes can gradually shift what is perceived as normal or acceptable (Vaughan, 1996).

Additionally, this case highlights the influence of systemic and operational pressures on decision-making. As shown in aviation maintenance research, decisions are often shaped not by individual negligence, but by organizational and operational factors that encourage continued operation within allowable limits (Munro & Kanki, 2003). The aircraft remained in service because it was legal to do so, but the broader operational context suggests that removing the aircraft from service earlier may have reduced overall risk exposure.

Role of the Pilot in Command

The PIC occupies a unique position within aviation ethics. Under FAR 91.3, the PIC has final authority and responsibility for the operation of the flight. This authority is not merely procedural—it is ethical.

The MEL may authorize dispatch, but it does not absolve the PIC of responsibility for the outcome. A Captain must be willing to say “no” when conditions warrant it, even in the face of operational pressure. This decision carries professional risk, potential scrutiny, and operational consequences. However, it is central to maintaining the integrity of the aviation safety system.

In the introductory scenario, the First Officer’s obligation is clear: report the discrepancy. The Captain’s responsibility is also equally clear: evaluate the situation objectively and ensure compliance. Anything less compromises both safety and professional integrity. What would you do?

Organizational Ethics and Safety Culture

Individual decision-making does not occur in isolation; it is shaped by the culture of the organization (International Civil Aviation Organization, 2013; Reason, 1997). Airlines that prioritize safety through a strong Safety Management System (SMS) create an environment where ethical decision-making is not only expected, but actively supported (Federal Aviation Administration, 2016). In these organizations that use SMS, safety is treated as a core value rather than a competing objective, which directly influences how MEL decisions are approached at every level. When leadership consistently reinforces that safety margins take precedence over operational efficiency, it establishes a standard that guides both maintenance and flight crews in real-world scenarios (Reason, 1997; ICAO, 2013).

Just Culture

A “just culture” is a critical component of that environment. It encourages open reporting of errors, concerns, and near-misses without fear of punitive action, provided those actions are not reckless or intentional (International Civil Aviation Organization, 2013; Federal Aviation Administration, 2016). In the context of MEL usage, this transparency is essential. Crews and maintenance personnel must feel empowered to question decisions, highlight concerns, or report trends without concern for backlash. Without that protection, there is a natural tendency to remain silent, which allows small issues to persist and potentially evolve into larger systemic risks (Reason, 1997).

Safety Data Systems

Data-driven safety programs provide the feedback loop necessary to identify and correct those risks (Federal Aviation Administration, 2016; International Civil Aviation Organization, 2013). Programs such as Flight Operational Quality Assurance (FOQA), Aviation Safety Action Program (ASAP), and Line Operations Safety Audit, allow organizations to move beyond anecdotal evidence and identify measurable trends in operational performance, including how MEL items are being used in practice (Federal Aviation Administration, 2004; Helmreich et al., 2001). These systems can highlight patterns such as repeated deferrals, operational workarounds, or decision-making under pressure, areas that may not be visible through compliance audits alone. When used effectively, they provide objective insight into how the system is functioning, not just how it is designed to function (ICAO, 2013; FAA, 2016).

Economic Pressures

The airline industry is under incredible pressure to produce financial results, maintain a regular schedule, and operate more efficiently than ever before. The key is managing these pressures and understanding how they affect decision making.

Safety is not mutually exclusive to profitability. Safety is the foundation upon which profit is made. If organizations don't run a safe operation, they won't operate long. Using the MEL outside of its established limit for short-term operational benefit may be tempting. But it will ultimately result in reduced safety margins and increased long-term risk, both operationally and financially. Long-term sustainability depends on balancing safety with other key performance indicators, while treating safety as the foundation for every decision.

Recommendations and Best Practices

1. Strengthen Ethical Training

Training programs should go beyond technical MEL knowledge and try and incorporate scenario-based decision-making that reflects real-world operational pressures. Integrating human factors and ethical frameworks helps crews recognize situations where legal compliance may not fully address the total risk picture (International Civil Aviation Organization, 2013; Federal Aviation Administration, 2016).

2. Encourage PIC Empowerment

Organizations must actively support PIC authority in operational decision-making. This includes supporting decisions that delay or cancel a flight for safety reasons when conditions exist. It is also critical to have support from organizational leadership, without

it this is simply theoretical and not operational (Federal Aviation Administration, n.d.; International Civil Aviation Organization, 2018).

3. Limit MEL Abuse

Tracking repeat deferrals and identifying systemic patterns can help prevent the gradual normalization of degraded operations. By using safety data to identify trends, organizations can intervene before routine acceptance of MEL items begins to erode safety margins (Federal Aviation Administration, 2016; Munro, D. & Kanki, B., 2003).

4. Improve Communication

Effective risk management requires collaboration between maintenance and flight crews. MEL decisions should not occur in isolation; instead, they should involve shared situational awareness and open dialogue to ensure the full operational context is considered (International Civil Aviation Organization, 2013).

5. Integrate Human Factors

MEL policies should account for human performance, not just technical compliance. Factors such as fatigue, workload, environmental conditions, and operational pressure all influence how a deferred item impacts the overall safety of the flight. Incorporating these considerations leads to more realistic and effective decision-making (Hobbs, 2008; Federal Aviation Administration, 2014).

Conclusion

The MEL is an essential tool in modern aviation, enabling operational flexibility without compromising safety, when it is used correctly. However, its ethical application depends completely on the judgment of the professionals who use it. Misuse of the MEL, whether

through normalization of deviance, operational pressure, or economic incentives, will gradually reduce safety margins. These risks are not immediately visible but accumulate over time, increasing the likelihood of failure. Ultimately, aviation safety is not preserved by regulation alone. It is sustained by the ethical judgment of pilots, maintenance personnel, and organizations. The MEL may define what is legal, but it is the responsibility of aviation professionals to determine what is right. In aviation, safety is not maintained by the minimum standard—but by the commitment to exceed it.

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